

polycaryoptic, indicating that WX154 and Double Rice have duplicate recessive genes for polycaryopsis (see table).

When the polycaryoptic line YA1, a selection from WX154/Tongilchal, was crossed with cytoplasmic male-sterile rice V20A, the F_1 was sterile. The F_1 was backcrossed to YA1. From this BCF_1 , polycaryoptic male-sterile plants could be selected (see figure), showing that the polycaryoptic line YA1 is a maintainer for cytoplasmic male-sterility, and that polycaryoptic male-sterile plants selected could be maintained by successive backcrosses to YA1.

Polycaryoptic male-sterile rice may have greater seed set because it has four stigmas instead of two. The possibility of using this male-sterile rice for F_1 hybrid seed production is being explored. □

Polycaryoptic male-sterile (A), polycaryoptic fertile (B), and normal (C) rice.

GENETIC EVALUATION AND UTILIZATION

Temperature tolerance

Effect of abscisic acid on rice seedling resistance to chilling injury

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Rice seedlings Dansheng No. 1, Guichao No. 2, and Shanyou No. 2 were studied for the effects of abscisic acid (ABA) on resistance to chilling injury influenced by hormonal regulation.

ABA accumulation varied with varietal resistance to chilling injury. Five days after the low temperature (8-10°C) treatment, seedlings of cold-resistant Dansheng No. 1 showed an ABA increase over cold-sensitive Shanyou No. 2. The longer the

Change in ABA content in the leaves of Dansheng No. 1 during low temperature.

Days of low temperature	ABA content (ng/g fresh wt)
0	0.65
3	13.50
6	20.60
9	58.50
LSD	0.08

low temperature lasted, the more ABA accumulated in leaves of the seedlings (see table).

Exogenous application of ABA reduced the symptoms of chilling injury such as the leakage of electrolytes from leaves and roots (see figure), leaf discoloration, and reduction of leaf fresh weight. ABA accumulation response should be investigated in further studies. □

Effect of ABA on leakage of electrolytes in chilled rice seedlings.

Pest management and control DISEASES

Sheath rot in the Punjab, India

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Sheath rot (ShR) caused by *Sarocladium oryzae* (Sawada) Gam. was first reported in India in Hyderabad (A.P.) in 1974 and in Kapurthala (Punjab) in 1980. *Fusarium* has been associated with sheath and panicle rot of rice for the last 3 years,

particularly on variety PR106, but was ignored and considered a secondary invader.

Fusarium symptoms resemble those produced by *S. oryzae*. They are oblong or irregular spots, 5-20 mm long with

reddish brown margins and grey centers, or they may be greyish throughout, on the upper leaf sheath. Lower sheaths also are affected and superficial pink powdery growth of the fungus is visible on all the sheaths. Infection reaches the stem and causes browning and rotting of the peduncle. Panicles partially emerge or remain inside the sheath. Emerged panicles have chaffy grains or partially filled, thin grains.

During 1982 kharif, ShR caused losses of up to 50%. Incidence was greater in heavy soils where more nitrogen was applied or where *Trifolium alexandrinum* was sown in rabi.

In 1981 and 1982, *Fusarium equiseti* (Corda) Sacc. and *F. moniliforme* Sheld. were isolated from rice leaf sheaths.

Pathogenicity tests were performed to confirm their association with ShR and panicle sterility. Plants were inoculated by injecting conidial suspensions, or by

Fusarium sp. symptoms. on sheath after inoculation.

inserting mycelial bits grown on potato dextrose agar into the boot leaf sheath before panicle emergence. Typical symptoms (see figure) appeared with both

methods, lesions developed within 1 week, and the sheath rotted in 3 weeks. Both *Fusarium* species caused disease and produced identical symptoms. □

Effect of azolla on rice tungro virus disease

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Farmers have worried that rice crops that receive azolla to augment nitrogen supply are severely affected by tungro virus disease (RTV).

Seeds of TN1 and IR36 were sown, 5 seeds/pot, in pots containing 400 g soils with and without azolla. TN1 is susceptible to RTV and the RTV vector green leafhopper (GLH) *Nephotettix virescens*. IR36 is resistant to RTV in the field, moderately susceptible in the greenhouse, and moderately resistant

to GLH. Ten days after sowing, seedlings were exposed for 24 h to viruliferous GLH that had fed on diseased plants for 4 days. Inoculation was done in cages with 4-5 viruliferous insects per seedling. IR36 and TN1 seedlings raised with and without azolla were exposed separately and together. Uninoculated plants of the same age were kept as control.

The percentages of RTV-infected seedlings were recorded 12 days after inoculation and plant height was measured (Table 1).

Mean values of RTV-infected seedlings between plants raised with and without azolla were almost the same within varieties. TN1 was severely infected and IR36

was moderately infected.

About 500 viruliferous *N. virescens* adults and nymphs were released on pots containing azolla. No insect survived beyond 3 days. The *azolla* did not develop disease symptoms.

A field experiment was conducted in four 5 × 2 plots with wire mesh along the bunds to prevent azolla flow. Azolla (*A. pinnata* and *A. caroliniana*) was incorporated at 10 kg/plot. Fifteen days later, when fresh growth of azolla was seen, TN1 and IR36 seedlings raised in an insect-proof area were transplanted two plots per variety, one with azolla and the other without. Plant spacing was 20 × 15 cm. Leaf yellowing symptoms similar to RTV were noticed on some TN1 hills 15

Table 2. Average percentage of RTV-infected seedlings, and seedling height, IRRRI.^a

RTV-infected seedlings (%)				Height (cm) of infected seedlings				Height (cm) of uninfected seedlings			
IR36 A ⁺	IR36	TN1 A ⁺	TN1	IR36 A ⁺	IR36	TN1 A ⁺	TN1	IR36 A ⁺	IR36	TN1 A ⁺	TN1
—	—	76.67	94.17	—	—	22.68	20.42	—	—	39.83	36.44
—	—	100.00	100.00	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
42.50	—	75.00	—	26.80	—	27.14	—	42.70	—	44.88	—
50.00	45.00	90.00	88.90	29.70	27.30	25.33	30.82	43.56	34.35	44.45	38.45
57.50	—	82.50	—	29.00	—	28.19	—	42.00	—	32.64	—
—	—	93.25	81.25	—	—	27.25	24.81	—	—	46.33	35.67
33.33	47.06	—	—	31.69	32.64	—	—	35.83	37.24	—	—
45.00	42.00	80.00	82.35	31.93	29.40	30.11	28.35	44.86	36.05	46.25	39.10
45.67	44.69	85.35	89.33	29.82	29.78	26.78	26.10	41.79	35.88	42.39	37.42

^aA⁺ = raised with azolla.